

MODERN SOLUTIONS FOR NASAL SEPTUM CORRECTION WITHOUT TAMPONADE AND THEIR DISADVANTAGES

¹Avazov Umrzoq Dilmurod o'g'li

²Yazdanov Zafar Nurali o'g'li

³Ishkuvatov Kamol Yarmamat o'g'li

⁴Juraqulov Muhammadali Mirsharof o'g'li

¹²³⁴Samarkand State Medical University, Department of Otorhinolaryngology No. 2, 1st year
clinical resident

Rasulova K.A

Scientific supervisor.

Assistant of the Department of Otorhinolaryngology No. 2, Samarkand State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14625930>

Abstract. Nasal diseases, which often significantly limit a person's quality of life, require careful diagnosis. To determine the causes of nasal congestion, rhinitis, snoring, sinusitis and headaches, our doctors use the most modern examination methods: nasal endoscopy, pressure measurement, rhinomanometry, computed tomography, X-ray examination of the paranasal sinuses.

Keywords: *Septum, Septoplasty, conservative and surgical methods.*

Relevance of the problem: Profile of a woman's face with closed eyes and makeup Septal surgery, nasal septum correction with reduction of the nasal turbinates, is the most common ENT surgery in adults. It solves problems such as impaired nasal breathing, snoring, and frequent infections of the maxillary and frontal sinuses. Typically, the surgery corrects two anatomical structures of the nose. First, the bone and cartilage structure of the nasal septum is corrected. Then, the turbinates (corpus cavernosa) are reduced to ensure air flow into the nose.

Research materials: During traditional operations with scissors, the turbinate tissue is reduced. At the end of the operation, tampons are inserted into the vascularized mucosa for 3-4 days to stop bleeding. Complications often arise when removing the tampons - the nasal septum, which has not yet been fully fixed, can become deviated again, as the tampon dries out on the newly operated site.

Research methods: It is impossible to breathe through the nose for three to four days after the operation.

The mucus secreted from the nose flows through the throat.

Tear fluid cannot drain through the nose, which causes bilateral tearing from the eye.
Impaired sinus ventilation creates pressure on the forehead and cheekbones.
Inpatient is required.

A new method of nasal septum correction - silicone splints

Observation method and materials: ct-small A new method of nasal septum correction is as follows: under general anesthesia, a small incision is made in the nasal septum, through which the cartilage and bone structure of the nasal septum is corrected. With this correction method, at the end of the operation, silicone plates are inserted to support (correct) the corrected septum, which are removed almost painlessly after 2-3 weeks (the patient can remove the plates at home, at the ENT doctor). A distinctive feature of this technique is that tampons are not inserted during these operations. This operation is an outpatient procedure.

Conclusion: The patient experiences almost no pain and usually breathes through the nose immediately after the operation.

Advantages of the new technique: dr-friedrich

Nasal breathing is usually possible immediately after surgery.

Only occasionally can you expect minor sleep disturbances.

The operation is performed on an outpatient basis;

The result of the operation is only a slight swelling of the nasal mucosa.

The patient only has minor nasal airway obstruction.

Silicone sheets do not dry out the wound and are easily removed.

REFERENCES

1. Abdurashidovich N. O., Zamonbek o'g'li B. F., Temirpulotovich T. B. Assessment of the relationship of the degree of conformity in patients with schizophrenia with clinical features and socio-demographic factors //European journal of modern medicine and practice. – 2024. – T. 4. – №. 2. – C. 22-30.
2. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 29-35.
3. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 545-550.

4. BegbudiyeV M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 551-557.
5. Biktimirova G., Turayev B., Ochilova N. Features of the pathokinesis of adaptation disorders in men with mild forms of cardiovascular disease //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 602-610.
6. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 558-563.
7. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 36-41.
8. Hamdullo o'g'li J. H., Temirpulotovich T. B. Features of the Clinical Course of Post-Traumatic Epilepsy, Psychiatric and Neurosurgical Approaches //International Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience and Psychology. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 8-14.
9. Hamdullo o'g'li J. H., Temirpulotovich T. B. Features of the Clinical Course of Post-Traumatic Epilepsy, Psychiatric and Neurosurgical Approaches //International Journal of Cognitive Neuroscience and Psychology. – 2024. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 8-14.
10. Ibragimova M., Turayev B., Shernazarov F. Features of the state of mind of students of medical and non-medical specialties //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D10. – C. 179-183.
11. Konstantinova O. et al. Experience in the use of thiamine (vitamin B1) megadose in the treatment of korsakov-type alcoholic encephalopathy //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 564-570.
12. Kosolapov V. et al. Modern strategies to help children and adolescents with anorexia nervosa syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 571-575.
13. Lomakin S. et al. Socio-demographic, personal and clinical characteristics of relatives of patients with alcoholism //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 278-283.
14. Murodullayevich K. R., Holdorovna I. M., Temirpulotovich T. B. The effect of exogenous factors on the clinical course of paranoid schizophrenia //Journal of healthcare and life-science research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 28-34.
15. Nematillayevna S. D. et al. Features of non-psychotic diseases and cognitive disorders in organic brain damage of vascular genesis in elderly people //Amaliy va tibbiyot fanlari ilmiy jurnali. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 124-130.

16. Nematillayevna S. D. et al. Prevalence of anxiety and depressive disorders in elderly patients //Scientific journal of applied and medical sciences. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 2. – C. 118-123.
17. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 413-419.